

Comparative analysis of the phonologic changes of Modern Persian under the influence of Turkish

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6652832>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022
Accepted: 02nd June 2022
Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

Vowel, consonant
phonemes, classical
Persian, system, modern

ABSTRACT

Linguists around the world think that the Persian language in Iran and its Dari and Tajik versions are considered to be dialects or distorted forms of Persian. The Dari and Tajik languages differ from Persian in appropriate vocabulary forms and syntax and in respect to taking from foreign languages. Dari has borrowings and copies introduced through the Hindi language and the Pashtu language. In the Tajik language there are lexemes and phrases that taken from Uzbek and Russian. Persian was influenced by Arabic and French at that time.

Classical Persian or Persian-Dari has been the language of official correspondence and flourishing literature of the time being in 3 dynasties, such as, Tohiry dynasty (ruled around Mavaraunnahr and Khurasan after secession from the Arabian Caliphate in the ninth century (821 - 873)), Saffori dynasty (included some parts of Seyistan, Khurasan and Movaraunnahr (873 - 903)) and especially in Samanids' dynasty (dominated in central Bukhara in the late 9th century (875 - 999))¹. Rudaki Samarkandiy, Ferdavsi Tusi, Abu Shukur Balkhi and other

Lax Vowels

A
I
U

many poets and writers used to write in Persian-Dari. This language is called Dari because of its conversion into "darbar" or "language of Palace" in independent Samanids state. But there is a different view to the etymology of the word.

The phonetic system of the classical Persian-Dari language differed from the modern Persian phonetic system. There were 24 consonant phonemes and 8 vowels in the classical Persian language². They are as followings:

Vowel phonemes

Tense Vowels

Ā
ī
Ū
Ē
Ō

¹ Drevnetyurskiy slovar. Izdatelstva "Nauka"
Leningrad, 1969. P. 3.

² Abulqāsemi, M "Dāstur-e tārixi-ye zabān-e fārsi".
Tehrān, 1385. p. 19

Constant phonemes:

P γ h y

B č z x w (x v)

T ĵ ž

D f m, n

S s w

K š r

G x l

Persian – Dari was mentioned as a direct successor of Middle Persian in the prologue to the “Farhang-e Fārsi” dictionary of M. Moeen and he gave an example from the “Shahnameh” of Firdavsi concerning the pronunciation method of that time³.

چو بشنید رستم سرش خیره گشت جهان پیش چشم

اندرش تیره گشت

همی بی تن و تاب و بی توش گشت بیفتاد از پای و

بی هوش گشت

بیر سید از آن پس که آمد بهوش بد و گفت با ناله

و با خروش

بگو تا چه داری ز رستم نشان که گم باز نامش

ز گرد نکشان

The Latin transcription of this extract can be as followings:

Ču bi-šniδ Rustam sar-aš xira gašt

A

E

O

Ā

I

U

Diftongs: ei, ow If we compare them with the classical Persian vowel system⁵, we can see the following changes:

C.P.L

Lax i →

u →

a →

M.P.L

e lax

o

a (e)

C.P.L

Tense i →

Ē

Tense ū →

M.P.L

i tense

u tense

Jihān pēši čašm andar-aš tira gašt

Ham-ē bē tan u tāb u bē tōš gašt

Biy-uftaδ az pāy u bē hōš gašt

Bi-pursid az ān pas ke āmad ba hōš

Baδ ō guft bā nāla u bā xurōš

Bi-gō tā čī dārē zi Rustam nišān

Ki gum bāδ nām-aš zi garden-kašān

If we compare the pronunciation of vowel phonemes in this extract and the pronunciation of the modern Persian vowel phonemes, we can see a considerable difference between them. For example:

“ču” → “čo”

“bi-šniδ → “be-šniδ

“xira” → “xire”

“jihān” → “jahān”

“peš-i” → piš-e

“ham-ē” → “ham-i”

“bē tōš” → “bē tuš”

It is natural to ask, how did the sharp difference between classical Persian and modern Persian vowels appear in the pronunciation of such vowels?

Modern Persian has 6 vowels and 2 diphthongs⁴. They are as followings:

³ Muin.M "Farhange Fārsi". Čāp-e hāštom. Tehrān, 1371

⁴ Bertels E. E. Tārix-e adabiyāt-e fārsi. Enteshārāt-e Hirmand. 1376

⁵ Abulqāsemi, M "Dāstur-e tārixī-ye zabān-e fārsi". Tehrān, 1385. p. 19

Ō

Tense ā →

ā long

The lax phoneme “i” in the classical Persian language has been transformed into a lax phoneme “e”, in modern Persian. The phoneme “u” has been transformed into the lax phoneme “o”. The lax phoneme “a” is

read in the form “a” at the beginning and at the middle of the word, but it has changed to the form “e” at the end of the word.

Examples:

C.P.L

M.P.L

Kitāb →

Ketāb

Rūstam →

Rōstam

Xira →

Xire

Tense phonemes:

Pēš-i →

piš-e

Pursiδ →

Pōrsid

Behōš →

Bihuš

Nerū →

Nirū

Jihān →

Jahān

Changes in the consonant phonemes are insignificant, but the phoneme ځ [δ] in the classical Persian was pronounced as “dz” in English. For example: “bi-šnid”, “bi-oftād” “bipursiδ”. The phoneme γ in the classical

Persian language has changed into the form of γ, q in modern Persian: For example: yorfe, noqte.

“xw” “x(v)” of Classical Persian is not preserved in modern Persian; For example:

C.P.L

M.P.L

xwāhar →

xāhar

xwaš →

Xoš

xwad →

Xod

xwēš →

Xiš

There are 8 letters in modern Dari⁶.

Lax Vowels

Tense Vowels

A

ā

I

ī

U

ū

⁶ Ilhām M. R. “Dastur-e zabān-e dari” Kābol, 1349. P. 5.

ē
ō

Examples of lax vowels:

A: abr, ba, man,

I: imroz, dil, isband

He: urdu, ustād, xud

Ā: āb, nān, mā

Ī: šīr, in, si

Ū: jūr, dū, tū

Ō: kōr, zōr, bōr

Ē: dēr, mēwa, sēr

If we compare the system of vowel phonemes in classical Persian with the system of vowel phonemes of modern Dari in Afghanistan and the Tajik phonemic system in Tajikistan, we can see that there is almost no difference between them⁷.

There is a question: when did the modern Persian vowel phonemes start to change and what was the reason for these changes? According to A.N. Boldirev from the end of the ninth to the beginning of the 16th century "the Persian literary language shows no indication of any local differentiation in the field of morphology, syntax and dictionary." Only from this period begins the division of three independent Persian, Dari and Tajik literary languages⁸.

Since the 16th century, phonological systems of these languages have also changed. This case still requires serious research, but it seems likely that there was an effect of Azerbaijani Turks in Iran.

It's obviously known from the history, since the 16th century the Turkish-speaking Safavids dynasty has ruled Iran. For this reason, many Turkish words were introduced into Persian, and it seems that the Persian phonological system was influenced by Turkish pronunciation.

The Turkish language is closely related to the the language of Azerbaijani Turks in Iran. The "Turkča-farsča genel sözlüğü", compiled by Jemshid Solehpur, shows that the Turkish vowel system consists of 8 phonemes⁹. These are:

Thin (lax) vowels	Thick (tense) vowels
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E i	a i
-----	-----

Ö ũ	o u
-----	-----

The front bilabial lax vowel "a" in the phonetic vowel system of Persian is absent in Turkish. Therefore, instead of the lax phoneme "a", taken from other languages, the phoneme "e" in Turkish is used. For example:

Arabic

Acāc →

Badan →

yalaba →

Xabar →

Hājat →

Turkish

Esas

Beden

Galabe

Haber

Hacet

⁷ Grammatikai zabāni adabii xāzirai tājik. Jildi . I. Dāniš, Dušanbe, 1985. P.4.

⁸ Boldirev A.N. Iz istorii razvitiya persidskogo literaturnogo yazika. – VYA, 1955. N 5. P. 78-92.

⁹ Sālehpur C. "Turkče-farsče" genel sözlugu. Tehran, 1375

Xadama →

Hademe

The lax phoneme "a" that comes at the end of classical Persian is pronounced as in Arabic and as a lax phoneme "a" in modern Dari and Tajik¹⁰. For example:

Persian	Dari	Tajik	Modern Persian
كهنه	Köhna	Köhna	kohne
ترجيمه	Tarjima	Tarjima	tarjome
ميوه	Meva	Meva	mive
جميله	Jamila	Jamila	Jamile
روسيه	Rusiya	Rusiya	Rusiye

As can be seen from the above examples, the lax vowel "a" in classical Persian has not changed in modern Dari and Tajik, but

the lax phoneme "a" has been transformed into the lax "e" in modern Persian. For example:

Modern Turkish

Galabe
Gamze
Gaye
Hademe

Modern Persian

yalabe
yamze
yāye
Xadame

The lax phoneme "a" at the end of the word is pronounced the same in classical Persian, modern Dari and Tajik, but it has changed to the lax phoneme "e" in modern Persian, which should undoubtedly be the effect of Turkish.

The denial particle "be" in classical Persian has not changed in the Dari and Tajik languages. But it has changed to the form of "bi" in modern Persian. Compare:

Classical Persian	Modern Turkish	Dari/Tajik	Modern Persian
Bebahra	bibehre	Bebahra	Bibahra
Be gāna	bi gāne	Begāna	Bigāne
Behöš	bihuš	Behöš	Bihuš
Bekas	bikas	Bekas	Bikas

As can be seen from these examples, the denial load came in the form of "be" in the classical Persian language and in Dari-Tajik, but it has changed to the form of "bi" in

modern Persian under the influence of the Turkish language.

Unlike classic Persian in modern Persian the lax phoneme "i" has been replaced by "e", but it has not changed in Dari.

Classical Persian

Rišvat
Rizā
Rikāb

Modern Persian

Rešvat
Rezā
Rekāb

Modern Tajik

Rišvat
Rizā
Rikāb

¹⁰ Bangu Og'lu T. "Turkçenin grameri" Ankara, 1998

Dil

Del

Dil

Zinda

Zende

Zinda

Zindān

Zendān

Zindān

The lax phoneme “o” in the classical Persian language has changed to a lax phoneme “o” in modern Persian, and it has not changed in Dari-Tajik.

Classical Persian

Modern Persian

Dari language

Dawlat

Doulat

Davlat

Rawšan

Roušan

Ravšan

Zubayda

Zubayde

Zubayda

Zardušt

Zardošt

Zardušt

Xurdan

Xordan

Xurdan

Xudāvand

Xodāvand

Xudāvand

Xujasta

Xojaste

Xujasta

It is not known how this lax phoneme “o” in modern Persian was replaced by a lax phoneme “o”, but it is noteworthy that the

words with the lax phoneme “o” in the Turkish language were accepted to modern Persian in the same form¹¹. Compare:

Ancient Turkish

Modern Persian

Classic Persian

Čogan

Čogān

Čavgān

čomaq

Čmāq

Čumaq

Monyul

Moyul

Moyul

But in other cases the short vowel “ö” of modern Turkish appears in the form “e”. For example:

Dewlet, zerdušt, čevgan.

The lax front phoneme “ö” of classical Persian has become a tense back phoneme “ū” in modern Persian. Compare:

Classic Persian

Modern Persian

Modern Dari – Tajik

Möy

Muy

Möy

Köy

Kuy

Köy

Böy

Buy

Böy

Jöy

Juy

Jöy

Jöja

Juje

Jöja

The tense phoneme “u” in the modern Persian language is pronounced close to the thick phoneme “u” in modern Turkish, but there is no evidence that the change of the short “ö” to the long “u” phoneme has the effect of the Turkish language.

In summary, we can conclude that the front lax vowel “a” in classic Persian which comes at the middle and at the end of the word has changed to the form of “e”, and the back lax vowel “e” has changed to the back lax phoneme “ı” in the Modern Persian

¹¹ Drevnetyurskiy slovar. Izdatelstva “Nauka” Leningrad, 1969.

language under the influence of the medieval Turkish language in Azerbaijan.

In all other cases modern Persian evolution requires further study.

Research shows that the phonemic system of the modern Dari and Tajik languages is

not much differ from the phonemic system of the classical Persian.

The phonemic system of the modern Persian has changed dramatically since the 16th century.

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